

Building data services for urgent applications

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Building data services for urgent applications

Goal: Integrate knowledge and data from multiple sources across geo-distributed heterogeneous resources to support decision making.

- Characteristics and requirements of Urgent Computing
- Programming data-driven pipelines over the Edge-to-cloud continuum
- Next steps in urgent data services for NSDF

Motivating use case

California's fast-moving Oak Fire burns 14,000 acres and forces thousands to evacuate outside Yosemite National Park

By Jason Hanna, Rebekah Riess, [Sara Smart](#) and Andy Rose, CNN

🕒 Updated 0645 GMT (1445 HKT) July 25, 2022

Could the exception become the rule? 'Uncontrollable' air pollution events in the US due to wildland fires

Liji M David^{1,2}
and Sonia Kreidenweis²

Published 22 February 2021 • © 2021 The Author(s). Published by IOP Publishing Ltd

Global challenges warrant Urgent Science

Weather and Climate

Hurricane Ida in New Jersey (September 21) – Sudden flooding pours months of rain in a few hours

Enabling forecasting models to specific socio-economic impact models affecting emergency management (fire & flood), sustainable agriculture and energy production.

Cyber-Attacks

Amazon Web Services
DDos Attack (Feb 2020) –
Peak traffic volume of 2.3 Tbps

Earthquake and Tsunamis

Acceleration of tsunami simulations to enable highly-accurate real-time analysis

Evacuation traffic patterns

Connected vehicles can't wait for the cloud to analyze a real-time situation before acting

Traffic jam caused by the evacuation from Hurricane Rita in Houston TX, September 23rd, 2005

Smart Factories

A command to shut down a motor has to be issued within milliseconds from detecting failures on the factory floor

Aeronautics

Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations of complex turbo-machinery and gearbox systems

A heterogeneous, diverse and distributed computing environment

The Edge-to-Cloud Continuum

Count = 10^9
Size = 10^1

Count = 10^1
Size = 10^9

EDGE COMPUTING
Closer to the data
Lower latencies
Limited & expensive
computation/storage
Unreliable connectivity

CLOUD COMPUTING
Far from data
Expensive data access
Relatively inexpensive
Seemingly infinite

Combining the right compute resources at optimal processing
points requires novel programming models

Urgent Computing

DEFINITION: Computing under **strict time** and **quality constraints** to support decision making with the desired confidence within a certain time interval

Balouek-Thomert, D., Caron, E., Lefèvre, L. & Parashar, M. (2022, November).
Towards a methodology for building dynamic urgent applications on
continuum computing platforms. In Combined International Workshop on
Interactive Urgent Supercomputing (CIW-IUS)

Motivation – Virtual Data Collaboratory

- **Increasing** variety, scales, resolutions, and availability of observational, experimental, and computational data

- Complex data-driven workflow formulations targeting discoveries **across domains and datasets**
- Users are still required to have certain domain knowledge about the facility to be able to **effectively find the data they need** (data silos)
- New data challenges for large facility-enabled science
 - Help users **discover new data and products** that they do not know a priori
 - **Intelligent discovery** and anticipatory delivery of data and products from large facilities to the users
 - **More effective and timely data discovery and access for composing workflows from multiple sources**
 - Need to **share, collaborate**: democratize data and CI
- Leverage **existing technical solutions/investments** addressing the urgency of connecting data sources, computing environments, and interdisciplinary researchers

Requirements of Urgent Computing

- Need to know the resources available
- Need to provision dynamically
- Need ability to monitor them
- Need ability to adapt
- Need ability to react

Urgent Applications need programming support to react to unforeseen events and system management to balance requirements and costs

Edge (Field cameras)

Smoke detection

Python client for
smoke detection

Event producer

Ephemeral file
system

- Images
- Confidence
in a smoke
event

Cloud (SDSC)

Wildfire Simulation

Simulator
Weather API

Latitude/Longitude
extractor

Event consumer

Event producer

Wildfire metrics
(severity, direction,
etc.)

Cloud (Utah)

Air Quality Models

Transport model for
pollution
concentration

Event consumer

In collaboration with Ismael Perez , Ilkay Altintas (SDSC) and Heather Holmes , Manish Parashar (Utah)

Building data-driven pipelines

Goal: Implementing dynamic policies for computation and data placement under uncertain environment conditions

Programming support

- Control-flow constructs
- Triggers based on availability of resources and content of the data

Resource management

- Actuation across the edge-to cloud continuum

Builds on edge middleware and autonomic features

2021 IEEE/ACM HPC for Urgent Decision Making (UrgentHPC)

Evaluating policy-driven adaptation on the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum

Year: 2021, Pages: 11-20

DOI Bookmark: [10.1109/UrgentHPC54802.2021.00007](https://doi.org/10.1109/UrgentHPC54802.2021.00007)

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“If this, then that.” (IFTTT) is a great example...

... and VDC has taken first steps towards programmable reactive behavior

Triggers

If New event added

With History of additions to your To Do List

When Filter code

Then Pause playback

And Post to channel

Queries

Actions

APPLICATIONS CATALOG

jupyter
Jupyter lab

Fakequakes (CSSI)

Object counter (SAGE)

Avian diversity

Whale detection

Structural Bioinformatics

User-defined Application

CREATE NEW APPLICATION

cf. Ivan Rodero's talk

Building data services for Urgent Applications on NSDF

UNDERSTAND THE VARIABILITY OF THE CONTINUUM

APPROACH: Measurements
and Benchmarks

RESEARCH OUTCOMES: Analytical Models

DELIVERING SOFTWARE ABSTRACTIONS FOR USERS

APPROACH: Adapting the application
logic to the infrastructure events

RESEARCH OUTCOMES:
Programming abstractions

PERSPECTIVES: THE OPEN ROAD AHEAD

SYSTEMS RESEARCH: Taking
processing to the data, not the other
way around

APPLICATIONS RESEARCH: Reducing
decision-making latency for a better
user experience

COLLABORATIONS: Managing
crosscutting dimensions

- Power consumption
- Security and Data privacy

SCIENTIFIC ANIMATION

Resources

Tutorial on Data-driven application development @eScience2022

<https://www.escience-conference.org/2022/tutorials/>

R-Pulsar middleware

<https://github.com/dbalouek/R-Pulsar>

Sage Smoke Detector Application:

<https://portal.sagecontinuum.org/apps/app/iperezx/wildfire-smoke-detection>

Smoke Detector Github: <https://github.com/iperezx/sage-smoke-detection>

WIFIRE: <https://wifire.ucsd.edu/>

Thank you

*Accelerate Science
Amplify Impact
Drive Innovation*

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